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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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**WITHOUT JUSTICE, LAW LABOURS IN VAIN:
A CRITIQUE OF THE JUDGMENT OF THE
SUPREME COURT OF NIGERIA IN *APC V.
BASHR SHERIFF & 3 ORS. (LAWAN v.
MACHINA) SC/CV/1689/2022***

By

Taiwo Olawoye Lawrence*

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Abstract

The central thesis of this critique is when technical justice is elevated to the status of judicial philosophy, it portends clear and present danger to the cause of social justice. Section 84 (1) of Nigerian Electoral Act 2022 requires every Political Party to choose its flag bearers for General Elections among its members through the party's primary elections which should be monitored by INEC. However, the parties' oligarchs more often seek to undermine this process. On many occasions this leads to the emergence of candidates who lack visions, charisma and integrity. This in turn may give rise to litigation. The pertinent question in this critique is; should the court cling to the mediaeval and mundane practice of forms rather than the substance? This study is an assessment of the judgment of the Supreme Court in *APC v. Bashir Sheriff* i.e. (*Ahmad Lawan v. Bashir Sheriff*). The study adopts the doctrinal method of examining primary and secondary sources of information including the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended), law reports, statutes, especially Electoral Act, 2022, internet culled materials and peer reviewed journal articles. The content is analysed. The study finds that apart from the fact that there is no internal democracy in the Political Party system in Nigeria, it is heart-breaking that the Supreme Court resurrected the marauding ghost of technical justice which has long been regarded as a relic of a bygone era. The study recommends that the Apex Court should not be seen as an undertaker of democracy. It should overrule itself at the earliest opportunity to ensure that the erroneous decision is not perpetuated. There can be no social justice unless the substance of the matter is examined on merit.

Key Words: Critique, Judgment, Justice, Law, Labour,

1. INTRODUCTION

*Law without justice, is a legitimation of tyranny. Justice, without law is fraught with anarchy. Justice riding law with a mission and vision arrives at destination.*¹

The case under consideration constitutes a source of worry for all the stakeholders in democracy and the administration of justice. The sanctity of judicial pronouncements especially from the Supreme Court of Nigeria (the Court) recently suffered a setback in the case under review. The Court gave a verdict that ensured that Ahmad Lawan, the second respondent in this case and former Senate President was declared as the Senatorial candidate of the appellant (APC) for Yobe North Senatorial District despite the notorious fact that he did not participate in the appellant's primary election conducted on May 28, 2022 where the first respondent emerged as a winner. The non-participation of the second respondent in the primary election was a result of the fact that he did not manifest the desire to go back to the Senate, having been there since the commencement of the fourth democratic republic over twenty-three years ago². This time, he desired to be President of Nigeria hence his deep involvement in the Presidential primary election conducted on June 8, 2022 by the appellant. However, since the judgment of the Court was delivered on February 6, 2023 nullifying the first respondent's victory at the primary election, this writer has been disturbed psychologically and has been trying to rationalise the decision without success. This exercise therefore sets out the facts of the case, the submissions of the counsel for the appellant and the first respondent, the resolution of the issues by the Court and of course, the expected uncomplimentary and derogatory public outcry for the manifest misgivings of the outcome of the judicial disputation. I have also highlighted areas of concerns with the decision, especially the premium placed on the pre-eminence of dry technicality over substantial justice which in many foreign jurisdictions has been consigned to the dustbin of a bygone era. Finally, it is recommended that the Court as

*Full Text of the Judgment of the Supreme Court in *Lawan v. Machina*. Available at <https://www.sabilaw.org>. Last visited 13/5/2023

**LL.B. (Calabar) Ph.D. (Ife) Senior Lecturer, Dept. of Jurisprudence and Private Law, Faculty of Law, O. A. U. Ile-Ife E-mail: taiwoolawoye62@gmail.com. Phone No. 08165298410.

¹ Musdapher Dahiru (2011). "The Nigerian Judiciary: Towards Reform of the Bastion of Constitutional Democracy". Being 2011 Annual Fellow Lecture of the Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, Lagos, p. 4

² Editorial Comment. *Guardiana Newspaper*, (Nigeria) "Dissecting the Supreme Court in *Lawan v. Machina*" Available at <https://www.guardian.ng>. Last visited 20/3/2023

the final Court and a court of policy should base its decision more on substantive justice than on technicalities. In so doing, the judiciary will continue to command the awe and respect it used to command.

2. THE FACTS OF THE CASE

The second respondent in this case, having been in the Senate as a lawmaker since the beginning of this fourth republic in 1999, manifested his desire to have a shot at the Presidency of Nigeria. Even though he is still eligible to contest for his former post as many times as he wishes but he bought the Presidential nomination and the expression of interest forms. This, it is assumed to permanently foreclose his Senatorial ambition pursuant to section 115(d) of the Electoral Act, No 13, 2022³. Another veteran politician, the first respondent who is also from the same Yobe North Senatorial District with the second respondent seized the opportunity of the second respondent's lack of interest in the Senatorial seat and aspired for the post. Meanwhile, amid the Presidential primary election, the appellant's national chairman, Abdullahi Adamu had announced the name of the second respondent as the consensus Presidential candidate for the party. This was repudiated by thirteen serving Governors from the northern region who declared their support for a southern aspirant for the sake of fairness and equity. Amid serious horse-trading for the Presidential ticket, the appellant's senatorial primary election for Yobe Senatorial District was conducted on May 28, 2022 which the first respondent won as the sole candidate.

Barely a day after he lost the Presidential primary election of the appellant, the second respondent activated his interest in the said Senatorial seat. Intense pressure was mounted on the first respondent to relinquish his primary win which he refused to do. The second respondent then mobilized the apparatus of the appellant in a bid to take the ticket from the first respondent. The appellant's leadership through a high wire political magic capitulated to the pressure and conducted another purported fresh primary on June 9, 2022 without informing the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), the electoral umpire, of its decision to so do, nor inviting it to monitor the purported fresh primary election as required by law⁴. The first respondent

³ The section provides that a person cannot sign a nomination paper or result form as a candidate in more than one constituency at the same election.

⁴ Section 84, Electoral Act, No. 13, 2022.

who had already won the primary election conducted on May 28, 2022 was said not to be the candidate of the appellant but the second respondent. The appellant's oligarchs discountenanced the primary poll conducted on May 28, 2022 which was monitored by INEC on the tenuous ground that Mr. Danjuma Manga, the appellant's official that chaired the May 28, 2022 primary election which produced the first respondent as the winner was not authorised to do so by the appellant's National Working Committee. In a move that defied logic and conventional wisdom, the appellant submitted the name of second respondent to the INEC which led to the initial omission of the appellant's candidate name from the INEC published particulars of candidates for the 2023 General Elections on the ground that the second respondent was not validly nominated. Since the first respondent refused to kowtow to the second respondent and the appellant had submitted the name of the second respondent to the INEC, the first respondent headed to the Federal High Court on June 22, 2022, and invoked the original jurisdiction of the lower court for a relief in line with the principle of *ubi jus ibi remedium*, for his declaration as the authentic Yobe North Senatorial candidate for the election on the platform of the appellant. He contended that the May 28, 2022 primary election that produced him was the only legitimate and valid primary election⁵. The other purported fresh primary election held on June 9, 2022 that produced the second respondent, he claimed, was fraudulent and therefore null and void. After hearing the contending parties, the trial court on September 28 2022 found in favour of the first respondent.⁶ It upheld his prayers *inter alia*, that the purported fresh primary election held on June 9, 2022 for Yobe North Senatorial seat was not monitored by INEC and therefore invalid⁷.

Aggrieved by the decision of the trial Federal High Court, the appellant filed an appeal at the Abuja Division of the Court of Appeal which upheld the judgment of the trial Federal High Court, on the ground that the purported fresh primary election of June 9, 2022, infringed on section 84 (1) of the Electoral Act 2022, which is designed to check political parties' act of impunity in the conduct of parallel primaries elections. The appellant being dissatisfied again further appealed to the Court which curiously

⁵ Full Text of the Judgment of the Supreme Court. Available at <https://www.Sabilaw.org>. Last visited 15/3/2023 p. 5

⁶ Ibid. p.6.

⁷ Ibid. p.6.

annulled the concurrent judgments of the trial Court and that of the Court of Appeal on February 6, 2023, on the ground that the first respondent adopted Originating Summons to invoke the jurisdiction of the Federal High Court rather than the Writ of Summons and declared the second respondent as the appellant's candidate for the Yobe North Senatorial seat.

3. ISSUES FOR DETERMINATION

The appellant raised six issues for determination out of which the Court considered the first issue as sufficient enough for the determination of the appeal⁸ to wit:

Whether in the circumstances of the appeal before the court below, especially with the allegation of fraud in the midst of other irreconcilable conflicts in the numerous affidavits, further affidavits filed by the parties in support of their various conflicting positions, the court below was correct to hold that the trial court was right to have adjudicated the first respondent's case on the first respondent's originating summons.⁹

In considering the appeal, the Court considered the propriety of the use of Originating Summons to invoke the jurisdiction of the trial Court for the ventilation of grievances of an aggrieved person¹⁰. Originating summons is used in respect of a matter where the facts are in substantial dispute between the parties and where allegations of crime, as it is in this case, were the fulcrum of the appellant's case. The appellant contended that the facts in the first respondent Originating Summons are not merely hostile but irreconcilably hostile such that it is wrong to invoke the jurisdiction of the court by way of Originating Summons¹¹. The learned senior counsel for the appellant therefore submitted that the lower court was wrong in upholding the decision of the trial Court that the Originating Summons procedure employed to invoke the jurisdiction of the trial Court was proper. The learned senior counsel further submitted that the lower Court failed to take into consideration the application of this legal principle to the fact of the case before it. According to the learned counsel:

⁸ Ibid., p.7

⁹ Ibid. p.7

¹⁰ Ibid p.29

¹¹ Ibid p.12

“the first respondent’s originating summons are not merely hostile but irreconcilably hostile to the extent that even the document tendered by the first respondent as exhibits in support of the reliefs he claimed raised more questions than answers and created self-doubts as to whether he is even the winner who was returned as the winner of the alleged primary said to have been conducted on May 28, 2022”¹².

The appellant’s counsel dwelt extensively on the allegations of fraud made by the first respondent¹³.

On the part of the first respondent, the learned senior counsel contended that the appellant did not controvert the deposition of Alhaji Danjuma Munga, a member of the Yobe state Senatorial Primary Election Committee appointed by the National Working Committee of the appellant who deposed to an affidavit that confirmed his membership of the committee that conducted the primary election of May 28, 2022, at the end of which the first respondent emerged as a winner¹⁴. The learned senior counsel further posited that the second respondent was an aspirant to the Presidential primary election conducted on June 8, 2022, and that the second respondent voluntarily in writing withdrew from the Yobe Senatorial primary election in order to contest in the Presidential primary election. The argument of the appellant that there were several allegations of fraud in the matter is described by the learned senior counsel for the first respondent as a figment of the imagination of the appellant. Finally, the learned counsel urged the Court to resolve the issue for determination in favour of the first respondent.

4. RESOLUTION OF THE ISSUE

In determining the appeal, the Court considered due process of law as one of the indicia to invoke the jurisdictional power of the trial court¹⁵. The Court cited the landmark pronouncement of Cotton L.J in *Re Giles and Personal Advance Co. v.*

¹² Ibid p. 12

¹³ Ibid.

¹⁴ Ibid p.27

¹⁵ Ibid p.28

Michell,¹⁶ where the purpose of the procedure of Originating Summons was explained as follows:

“to enable simple matters to be settled by the court without the expenses of bringing an action in the usual way, not to enable the court to determine matters which involve a serious matter”¹⁷

The Court further explained the domain of the Originating Summons citing its earlier decision in *Hussani Isa Kirs; v. Salisu Dan Asumi Mohammad*¹⁸ in the following words:

“In effect, originating summons is a procedure wherein the evidence is by way of documents and there is no serious disputes as to their existence in the pleadings. It is usually heard on affidavit evidence and involves questions of law rather than issue of facts”¹⁹.

By the above proposition, according to the Court, Originating Summons is best suited for cases where there are no substantial dispute of facts or likelihood of facts.²⁰ The Court also cited the case of *Standard Cleaning Company v. Council Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife*²¹, where the principle was reiterated in the following words;

“Originating summons should only be applicable in circumstances where there is no dispute on the question of facts or even the likelihood of such dispute. Application for initiating contentious issues of facts, where the facts of the plaintiff leave matter for conjecture, originating summons is not appropriate procedure”.²²

After considering the facts of the case *vis-à-vis* its commencement by Originating Summons, the Court by a split decision of three to two on February 6, 2023, delivered

¹⁶ (1890)43 Ch. D 391

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ (2017)17 NWLR (pt. 1594) 181.

¹⁹ Full Text of the Judgment of the Supreme Court on *Lawamv. Machjna. Op .cit.* p.31

²⁰ *Ibid.* p. 32.

²¹ (2011)14 NWLR (pt.1269)103

²² *Ibid* at pp. 204-205

by Justice Cletus Chima Nweze ruled that the second respondent who did not participate in the only valid primary election of May 28, 2022 was the appellant's candidate for the Yobe North Senatorial District. The Court did not adduce any reason for departing from the established precedents that admonished against the philosophy of technical Justice instead of substantial justice to all matters brought before it. This decision, in no small way, negatively impacts the Court's standing. The majority hinged their decision on the technical jaw-dropping premise that the lower Courts lacked jurisdiction to question bare-faced mockery of democracy perpetrated against the first respondent because Originating Summons was the wrong form of action by which he commenced the proceedings and which the Court described as a "parade of abysmal ignorance as to what to do on the part of the senior counsel to the first respondent"²³.

5. COMMENTS

A rhetorical question which is necessary at this stage is; where is the institutional memory of the Court for it to have forgotten that it had issued words of caution in plethora of cases on constraining adherence to technicality?²⁴ The crux of the matter was whether the second respondent could have lawfully participated in the two primaries in the same election. It is humbly submitted that the Court failed to provide the answer to this question but chose to dissipate its energy on an innocent issue. Not only does the extant Electoral Act 2022 frown upon double or multiple nominations of a candidate for primary elections but it also criminalizes such acts. By its judgment, the Court clothed the illegality of the appellant with judicial approval by declaring the second respondent the authentic candidate of the appellant at the expense of the constitutionally guaranteed right of the first respondent²⁵. However, the two dissenting justices, Adamu Jauro and Akomaye Agim rekindled our hope that our quest for equity and social justice is not after all a wild goose chase. The duo disagreed with the majority decision and held that both the trial court and the appellate court were correct in their findings and declaration of the first respondent as the appellant's

²³ Full Text of the Judgment, op. cit p.50.

²⁴ *Yusuf v. Adegoke & anor* (2011) LPELR 9199 (CA) 2024, *Akeredolu v. Abraham & ors* (2008) 5 NWLR (pt. 1080) 227, *Amechi v. INEC* (2008) All FWLR (pt. 407) 1. (2008) 5 NWLR pt. 1080) 227

²⁵ Dissecting the Supreme Court in *Lawan v. Machina* (2) Editorial Comment, *The Guardian Nigeria*, and Available at <https://www.guardian.ng>.

Senatorial candidate for Yobe North Senatorial District²⁶. They were pungent in their decision when they held that:

“the conduct of another primary on June 9, 2022 where the second respondent emerged was in breach of section 84 (5) of the Electoral Act, 2022, and section 285 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as the APC never cancelled the one held on May 28, 2022”²⁷.

The reason why the Court trod the path of technicalities rather than substantial justice remained within its exclusive knowledge. A pertinent emerging question that arises is; of what judicial values are technicalities to administration of justice? In his reaction to the outcome of the case, the second respondent expectedly exalted the judgment of the Court, describing it as a “victory for the entire country and democracy”²⁸. According to him:

“I want to commend the Supreme Court and in fact the judiciary for delivering this kind of judgment to strengthen our democracy”.²⁹

Contrary to this narrow and subjective assessment, it is our considered opinion that the judgment of the Court is neither a victory for the country nor democracy. Instead, it is a disgrace to the country within the global community of democracies, a mockery of democracy, a travesty of justice, and a vintage testimony of our stunted growth in democratic culture which was re-enacted twenty-four years ago.

6. NON – COMPLIANCE WITH RULES OF COURT

It is true that the Federal High Court Practice Direction provides that pre-election matters be instituted by way of Originating Summons while the Federal High Court (Civil Procedure) Rules 2019 provide for the commencement of proceeding where the

²⁶ “Yobe North: Appeal Court Affirms Bashir Machina As APC Candidate.” Available at <https://www.channelstv.com> Last visited 20 /5/2023.

²⁷ .Ibid.

²⁸ Ugwu Francis (2023) *Lawman v. Machina*, “Supreme Court Judgment Sparks Controversy”. Available at <https://www.dailypost.ng>. Last visited 12/3/2023

²⁹ *Ibid*

claims are based on or includes an allegation of fraud by Writ of Summons.³⁰ It is also true that the first respondent commenced his action with the former instead of the latter. It is therefore relevant here to know the meaning of the rules of court and the effect of non-compliance with them.

The rules of court are part of the machinery of justice made by the courts to regulate their proceedings. They are designed to assist in obtaining justice with ease and certainty.³¹ Pursuant to section 18(1) of Interpretation Act³², they are akin to subsidiary legislations and consequently have the force of law. As a general rule, the rules of courts must be obeyed by litigants. In *Duke v. Akpabuyo Local Government*³³, the Court emphasised the importance of the rules of court. However, it must be noted that not every non-compliance with the rules of courts is necessarily fatal to the case of a litigant. It is trite law that the rules of courts must never be interpreted to defeat the course of justice and where the effect of strict adherence to a provision of rules of court will hinder the Court from performing its primary duty of doing substantial justice, the Court must ignore the provision in favour of substantial justice³⁴. The Supreme Court has been consistent in reiterating this principle in litany of cases. For instance, in the case of *Federal Government of Nigeria v. Zebra Energy Ltd*³⁵, the Court stated;

Procedure is a guide to smoothen the passage of suit; to direct the parties what to do and to guide the court to arrive at the justice of a case. The court shall never be shackled by procedure, the case is not made for a procedure, it is the other way round. Once the procedure employed has brought into focus the issues the parties contest and there is no miscarriage of justice, it will not matter that the procedure is not the correct one ...³⁶

Earlier in 1989, the Court also stated that:

³⁰ Order 3 r. 2 (b)

³¹ Idowu O. Ifedayo (2023) "The Supreme Court of Nigeria and The Stain of Justice by Technicalities: Why *APC v. Machina* is wrong". Redeemer's University Nigeria. *Journal of Jurisprudence and International Law (RUNJI)*. Vol. 3 2023 p. 9

³² Cap. 123 LFN, 2004

³³ (2005) 19 NWLR (pt. 959) 130

³⁴ Idowu O. Ifedyo op.cit p. 10

³⁵ (2002) 18 NWLR pt. 798, 162

³⁶ *Ibid.* per Belgore (JSC) at pp. 204-205.

“Rules of procedure are made for the convenience and orderly hearing of cases in court. They are made to help the cause of justice and not to defeat justice. The rules are therefore aids to the court and not masters of the court³⁷.

The cumulative effect of the above holdings of the Court is that any non-compliance with the rules of court is *prima facie* irregular but not a ground for nullity unless such non-compliance amounts to a denial of justice or affects substantial justice. In the more recent case of *Ofoegbunam v. Okongwu*³⁸, the Court held that;

“Non-compliance with the mandatory provisions of an Act is fatal, whereas, non-compliance with the rules of court may be an irregularity which can be waived... Non-compliance at the beginning of the process cannot be condoned or corrected but the non-compliance that can occur and can be corrected in the cause of the action can be condoned”³⁹.

It is conceded that adherence to legal rules and procedures must be followed, at least, to ensure consistency and predictability in the administration of justice. However, when the rules and procedure are likely to produce absurd outcomes, as stated earlier, the court must exercise its inherent power to make amend which it deems fit as the occasion demands. It is along this line of reasoning that Hon. Justice Aniagolu (JSC) stated that:

“the laws of our land enjoin us to do that... while respecting procedural regularity, we must do substantial justice with power to make amendment which are deem fit or not as the occasion demands”⁴⁰

In the case under review, the Court appears to hold an uncompromising position insisting on rigid rules on commencement of action that must be followed. However, this author recently criticised the Court for its reliance on technicality in the case of *Ude Jones Udeogu & 2 ors v. (Orji Kalu’s case)*⁴¹, where the Court repudiated the judgment of the Court of Appeal on the ground that the judge who heard the case at the trial court even though the same biological person is not the same juridical person

³⁷ *UTC (Nig) Ltd v. Panmotei* (1989) 2 NWLR (pt. 103) 244, per Belgore (JSC) at p. 296

³⁸ (2018) LPELR 45086 (CA)

³⁹ *Ibid*

⁴⁰ *Okeowov. Millipore* (1979) 12 NSCC p. 210

⁴¹ SC 622c /2019.

at the Court of Appeal. The first is a judge of the High Court, and the latter, is a justice of the Court of Appeal- mere technicality? In that case, this writer justifiably affirmed that the Apex Court of the golden era⁴² had always been determined to provide remedy based strictly on the justice of the case. To justify this, the Court of that era in *Bello v. A.G. (Oyo State)*⁴³ held that:

“I think the court has attained a status in the pursuit of justice that a claimant who has a recognised injury cannot be turned back on the ground that he has not stated the head of law under which he was seeking remedy”⁴⁴.

It is submitted respectfully that the judgment of the Court in the instant case is a testimony that the Court deliberately chose to depart from the golden era which veteran legal practitioners of those days fondly remember with nostalgia. The decision of the Court in this case invoked the 13th -century notions about the English common law which believed that no matter how good your case is, it can be thrown out on technical grounds. The Court by its decision in the instant case, insulted the sensibilities of rational thinking Nigerians by hanging its decision on the fact that the first respondent’s learned counsel should have commenced the matter by Writ of Summons instead of Originating Summons because of allegations of fraud. The outrageous effect of the judgment is that the court rewarded a person who did not participate in a beauty pageant with wining and dismissed a participant who scored the highest points. The Court should have in our view, leaned more on the side of equity which is part of our received laws and which evolved as a result of this typical constraining adherence to abstract technicalities.

7. THE TRIUMPH OF TECHNICALITY

The Court’s judgment under review is a typical metaphor for technical justice which has always failed to deliver social justice. Recall that the trial court considered the

⁴² The golden era of the Supreme Court was between mid-1970 to late 1980 when the military held sway in governance. During this period, certain select core of jurist were elevated to the court who had their strengths not only in law, but also in classis, philosophy, and other courses in humanity. It was the period when the court gave life to the muffled aspiration of the people, to secure their freedom and liberty even in the midst of clash of arms. Some of the eminent jurists were Chukwudifu Oputa (JSC), Kayode Eso (JSC), Otutu Obaseki (JSC), Chukwuemeka Edie (JSCC) etc.

⁴³(1986) 5 NWLR (pt. 45) 828

⁴⁴ Ibid at p. 876

merit of the case. So also was the appellate Court. The Apex Court did not advert its mind to the facts of the case at all. Recall also that the appellant (APC) and the second respondent did not deny the following facts;

- (a) That the second respondent did not participate in the party's Senatorial primary election for Yobe North Senatorial District conducted on May 28, 2022 which was monitored by INEC.
- (b) That the second respondent through a written letter voluntarily withdrew from the primary of the appellant for Yobe Senatorial District on May 28, 2022.
- (c) That the second respondent secured nomination forms for Presidential primary and Senatorial primary elections of Yobe North Senatorial Districts contrary to section 84(5) of the Electoral Act 2022 and section 285 of the 1999 CFRN.
- (d) That the INEC was not invited to, nor monitored the purported second fresh primary election of the appellant held on June 2, 2022 which allegedly produced the second respondent as the Senatorial candidate for the said Senatorial District.

What then are the material facts on which the Court, by its majority decision predicated its judgment? It is our view that it is no other than the form of commencement of the case. A careful review of the facts reveals that one does not need to consult a clairvoyant, nor be as wise as Biblical King Solomon to discern that the majority judgment of the court is anchored on dry technicality spurred by the social status in life and position in society of the second respondent⁴⁵. Rather than resolve the fundamental issues that touched the root of the case, the Court is more fixated on the letters of Originating Summons and the allegation of fraud made by the first respondent⁴⁶. What the court is constitutionally requested to do is to do justice between the two consumers of justice as to their respective rights regard being had to the facts of the case.

⁴⁵ He was the Senate President of the 9th National Assembly at the time with a lot of influence to peddle and patronages to leverage on.

⁴⁶ Editorial comment. *The Guardian, Nigeria*. Available at <https://www.guardian.ng>. Last visited 22/8/2023.

Black's Law Dictionary defines justice as "the fair and proper administration of laws."⁴⁷ Similarly, substantial justice is referred to as "justice fairly administered according to the rules of substantive law regardless of any procedural error not affecting the litigant's substantive rights, a fair trial on the merits."⁴⁸ From the above definitions, it means that until administration of justice is carried out in fairness, it cannot be said that justice has been done and as such the courts are duty-bound to uproot at all cost every stumbling block on the way of substantial justice. This is in line with a popular *cliché*, "let justice be done though the heaven falls"⁴⁹. Along the same trajectory, the doctrine of equity which is part of our heritage from the English legal system admonishes that justice must be administered in accordance with what is fair and just in all circumstances. It therefore follows that until and unless decisions of courts follow these dictates of the doctrine of equity, justice is meaningless. Thus, on the basis of the requirements of both common law and the doctrine of equity, the majority decision of the Court cannot be sustained on the grounds of fairness, equity and justice but a veritable example of perverse judgment and crass legalism.

Closely related to our present discourse is the concept of technical justice. The Court of Appeal in the case of *Benedict Orji V. Ozo Nne illoputaife & ors*⁵⁰ described the term to mean "immaterial, not affecting the substantial right, without substance"⁵¹. Late Hon. Justice Niki Tobi (JSC) in the case of *Yusuf v. Adegoke & anor*⁵² held that:

A technicality in a matter could arise if a party is relying on abstract or inordinate legalism to becloud or drown the merits of a case. A technicality arises if a party quickly takes an immediately available opportunity, however infinitesimal it may be, to work against the merits of the opponent's case. In other words, he holds and relies tenaciously on the rules of court with little or no regard for the justice of the matter. As far as he is concerned, the rules must be followed to the last

⁴⁷ The Ninth Edition of the Black's Law Dictionary p. 942

⁴⁸ *Ibid.* p.943.

⁴⁹ The Motto of Ferdinand 1 Holy Rom an Emperor 1, (1556-1564) who used it as his slogan and it became an important rule to control the Nation.

⁵⁰ (2011) LPELR 9199 (CA) 2024

⁵¹ *Ibid.*

⁵² (2007) LPELR 3534 (SC)

sentences, the last words, and last letters without much ado, and with little or no regard for the injustice that will be caused to the opponent⁵³.

It is the respectful submission of this writer that this is what the counsel for the appellant capitalised on. He fully exploited the technical error made by the first respondent's counsel to becloud and drown the merit of the case. He also did not care about the injustice that may be the outcome of the case. There can be no better description of what the learned Senior Counsel for the appellant wanted to be the outcome of the case when he vehemently relied on inordinate, inconsequential and abstract legalism to work against the merits of the case. Apart from what the learned Hon. Justice Chima Nweze who delivered the lead judgment described as a parade of abysmal ignorance as to what to do on the part of the first respondent's counsel⁵⁴, the appellant's counsel sought for other categories of technical errors. For instance, what is the significance of the true name of the first respondent to the case when there is no other claimant of the name?⁵⁵ What is the evidential value of the true identity of the Senatorial District in the case when Yobe state is not replicated in the country?⁵⁶ All the submissions of the counsel for the appellant and the second respondent were technical bait with hooks which the Court uncritically swallowed without averting its mind to the essence of substantial justice. This certainly is to the discontent of reasonable members of the Nigerian society.

It must be borne in mind that the practice of technical justice is rooted in common law of England which we adopted as part of our laws⁵⁷. By its nature, it is uncompromisingly rigid and technical. However, with the emergence of equitable jurisdiction, justice has been made to focus on fair and just outcomes in order to palliate the rigid effect of the common law. The legendary Lord Alfred Denning M.R in his characteristic fashion has since 1949 in the case of *Seaford Court Estate v. Asher*⁵⁸ warned judges on the danger engendered by undue adherence to technicality. In the administration of justice, according to his lordship;

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ Full Text of the Judgment of the Court op. cit. p. 50

⁵⁵ Ibid. p.15

⁵⁶ Ibid p.11

⁵⁷ By virtue of the Statutes of General Application in force in England as at January 1, 1900

⁵⁸ (1949)2 K.B. 481

“The English language is not an instrument of mathematical precision” in consequence of which “a judge should not be ... a mere mechanic in the power house of semantics. He should be the man in charge of it”⁵⁹.

This in turn reinforces the need for judges to subordinate technicalities to the over-arching need to engender substantial justice. Hon. Justice Chukwudifu Oputa (JSC) was also no less emphatic on the damage which reliance on technicality fosters on dispensation of justice. He cogently put it in the following words:

“The picture of law and its technical rules triumphant and justice prostrate may no doubt have its admirers. But the spirit of justice does not reside in forms and formalities, or in technicalities, nor is the triumph of the administration of justice to be found in successfully picking one’s way between pitfalls of technicality. Law and all its technical rules ought to be but a handmaid of justice and legal inflexibility... may, if strictly followed, only serve to render justice grotesque or even lead to outright injustice. The court will not endure that mere form or fiction of law, introduced for the sake of justice, should work a wrong, contrary to the real truth and substance of the case before it”⁶⁰.

Thus, these preceding *obiter dicta* of the eminent justices reinforce the need for judges to subordinate technicality to the over-arching need to do substantial justice.

As if this is not strong enough, the Supreme Court in *Daphanlong v. Dearie*⁶¹ further stated as follows:

“The reign of technical justice is over, on the thrown now sits substantial justice, long may you reign, substantial justice”⁶²

⁵⁹ Lord Demining. (1979) *The Discipline of Law* (Butterworth 1979) at 56-57

⁶⁰ Per Hon. Justice Chukwudifu Oputa (JSC) in *Bello v. Attorney – General of Oyo State*, (1986) 5 NWLR (Pt. 450), 828 at 886. In the same case, Hon. Justice Kayode Eso (JSC) echoes the same message reinforcing the need for judges to approach their constructionist task with an eye on substantial justice. According to him, “it would be tragic to reduce judges to a sterile role and make an automation of them. I believe it is the function of judges to keep the law alive, in motion, and to make it progressive for the purpose of arriving at the end of justice, without being inhibited by technicalities, to find every conceivable, but acceptable way of avoiding narrowness that spells injustice. Short of being a legislator, a judge, to my mind, must possess an aggressive stance in interpreting the law”

⁶¹ (2008) 15 NWLR (pt. 1036) 332.

⁶² *Ibid.*

No doubt, substantial justice did not reign in this case, it is a triumph of technicality.

8. CONSEQUENCES OF TRIUMPH OF TECHNICALITY

The consequential result of reliance on the philosophy of technicality in the administration of justice cannot be underestimated. The Court's statements in some epochal cases incidentally are testimonies. For instance, in the case of *Akeredolu v. Abraham & ors*⁶³, the Court held that:

“Technicality in the administration of justice shuts out Justice. A man denied justice on any ground, much less a technical ground, grudges the administration of justice, it is, therefore, better to have a case heard and determined on merit than to leave the Court with a shield of ‘victory’ obtained on mere technicalities”⁶⁴

In *Ameachi v. INEC*⁶⁵, the Court on the contrary reiterated the philosophy of substantial justice when it held that;

“the court has a standing and rigid invitation to do substantial justice in matters brought before it. Justice to be dispensed by this court must not be inhibited by any paraphernalia of technicalities”⁶⁶

It is to be noted that the above *dictum* of admonition on the evils of technical justice emanated from the Court itself. The relevant question which is worth repeating again is; why did the court depart from its previous words of caution on technical justice? Can we attribute it to institutional amnesia? Is it a deliberate decision of the justices who delivered the majority judgment to sacrifice the long tradition of *stare decisis* on the altar of social status of the second respondent? Whatever be the motive of the Court, the fact is that the majority judgment in the case, particularly given the fact that no reason was adduced for departing from established precedents brought the Court to a manifest disrepute. The learned justices of the Court should have loosely interpreted the term "fraudulent" as contained in the first respondent's petition since the substance of the case was on whether the first respondent was the rightful Senatorial candidate of the appellant in the said Senatorial District. Not only this, the

⁶³ 2018) LPELR44067 (SC)

⁶⁴ Ibid

⁶⁵ (2008) 5 NWLR (pt. 1080) 227

⁶⁶ Ibid, per Aerie (JSC) at p. 449

public outcry that trailed the judgment is expectedly derogatory and uncomplimentary. Just when members of the public were trying to forget the seeming illogicality or judicial abracadabra performed by the Court in the Imo state Gubernatorial Election Petition in 2019⁶⁷, the Court further worsened its unenviable perception by its judgment in this case. This writer holds the view that any dispensation of justice with question marks in the minds of reasonable members of the society even when it is delivered with the best of legal intentions is no justice. It is therefore submitted that the Court is in serious error to have decided the case on technical ground instead of its peculiar facts. The ensuing corollary is that the judgment has led to the emergence of a judicial legislation of bad law which is binding on all the lower courts in Nigeria. Good law, it is believed must have human face. It must not patronize technicalities, nor encourage a situation where a party in litigation will only return home with Pyrrhic victory which in reality is no victory.

The impact of technical Justice on clients is no less important. It is a notorious fact that a good practice of law is that the inarticulate ignorance of the counsel should not determine the outcome of the action before the court⁶⁸. In other words, the sins of the counsel should not be visited on the litigants. A party to an action should not suffer adversely as a result of the procedural flaws made by counsel⁶⁹. In the case of *Bello v. A-G (Oyo state)*⁷⁰. The Court reiterated the position that the Court will not visit the carelessness of counsel on the clients.⁷¹ According to this lordship;

“I think I am speaking the minds of all engaged in the administration of justice... that the day the courts allow the inarticulate ignorance of counsel to determine the result of an action before it, that day will herald the unconstructive genesis of the unwitting enthronement of injustice aided by the court itself in default”⁷².

Similarly in the earlier case of *Doherty v. Doherty*⁷³, the Court found that failure to comply with the conditions of appeal is entirely due to the fault of counsel. “To shut

⁶⁷ In this case the person who came fourth in the electoral contest was declared the eventual winner on the evidence of a witness who conjured votes from the ghost

⁶⁸ Idowu O. Ifedayo (2023) op. cit p. 15

⁶⁹ Ibid p. 15

⁷⁰ op. cit

⁷¹ Ibid

⁷² Ibid, per Karibi Whyte (JSC) at p. 871.

⁷³ (1964) 1 All N. L. R. 299.

them out from hearing of the appeal on merit is to hold them personally responsible for the negligence of their solicitors”⁷⁴. It is conceded that the Court remarked that even if the Federal High Court Practice Directions provide that pre-election matters be instituted by way of Originating Summons, it is not enough reason to disregard the need to adopt the appropriate form of commencement of the action⁷⁵. It is also not denied that counsel to the first respondent erroneously instituted the case by Originating Summons contrary to the provisions of Federal High Court (Civil Procedure) Rules. It is however submitted that the Court completely undermines the non-personal liability of clients as a result of ‘inarticulate ignorance’ of the first respondent’s counsel, clinging tenaciously to dry technicalities. The first respondent in this case is as a result, lost his peoples’ mandate at the primary level to an ‘impostor’ who voluntarily withdrew from the Senatorial race, opting for Presidential Primary and subsequently made a *volte face*.

Apart from disturbing the existing balance of judicial precedent, the Court’s judgment under review also legitimizes the act of impunity of the appellant which capriciously replaced a duly nominated aspirant with its preferred candidate. While it is accepted that this kind of behaviour is not peculiar to the appellant, it is worth stating that any party system that permits such recklessness lacks the moral authority to lead the nation. The ideal is that political parties should embrace internal democracy and allow it to flourish. The party can subsequently use it as a spring board to seeking to serve the larger society⁷⁶. This is because one cannot give what he does not have (*Nemo dat quod non habeat*). The Court should have scolded the appellant for its act of impunity instead of applauding it and rewarding its preferred candidate with the exalted position of the Hon. Member of the Senate. The Court against all known traditions of impartial adjudication descended into the arena of conflict by failing to make a definitive statement against the reckless behavior of the appellant to serve as deterrent to other political parties but went about chasing the wind and getting an absurd result from it.

⁷⁴ Ibid. per Coker (JSC) at p.301. See also the following cases *Nadine v. Nwadike* (1987) 4 NWLR (pt. 65) 394 and *A.C. B. v. Elosiuba* (1991) 3 NWLR (pt. 178) 133.

⁷⁵ Idowu O. Ifedayo (2023). op.cit. p.9

⁷⁶ “Dissecting the Supreme Court in Lawaqa v. Machinaq” The Editorial Comment. *The Guardian*, Nigeria. Available at <https://www.guardian.ng>. Last visited 15/3/2023.

9. CONCLUSION

This is a dispassionate critique of the judgment of the Court in the case of APC v. Sheriff Machina. The critique looks into the propriety of the decision of the Court in the case especially with respect to uncompromising adherence to medieval judicial philosophy of ascendancy of technicality over substance. It is not in the least, to impugn the integrity of the Hon. Justices of the Court. The paper humbly concludes that to focus on forms of commencement of action instead of the merits of the case is a retrogressive journey to the 13th-century English system when rigid common law held sway to the extent that judges refused to allow a man to stay in a house he built. Equity, conscience, good faith and substantial justice at that time were sacrificed on the altar of common law rigidity. The majority decision of the Court in this case is like a next of kin to the case of Hon. Rotimi Amaechi v. INEC because the facts are all on fours. In the former case, a candidate who did not participate in the primary election of the appellant was declared the winner while in the latter, a candidate who did not campaign nor contest the election under his party, Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) was declared the winner.

Whatever misgivings any one may have about the judgment or whether the Court has administered justice or not in the instant case, the law is what the Court says it is at any particular time. It is also binding on the lower courts as a result of judicial convention of stare decisis. Nevertheless, this writer is strongly of the view that the judgment of the Court is not only retrogressive, it is odious as it is a denigration of democracy in Nigeria. The decision seems to suggest that whoever the political oligarchs want, they can whimsically impose him as a candidate whether the person wins primary election or not. The decision of the Court further judicialises politics and creates a situation that looks like it is unelected judges who determine those who rule, not the electorates. This also creates a high sense of frustration about the prospect of consolidating democracy in Nigeria. Section 33 of the Electoral Act 2022 is very clear in a situation where it becomes imperative for a political party to substitute candidates. The facts of this case do not disclose either of these situations. The judgment, with great respect, is therefore a judicial coup against the first respondent. This is because it is class based due to the social status of the second respondent. The declaration of the second respondent as the ultimate winner of the primary election in which he did

not participate, is a monumental error which betrays the cause of substantial justice and portrays the Court as a super Santa claus (Father Christmas). This writer believes that the decision was reached per incuriam. Nevertheless, the consolation is that the Court did not set out to disturb the balance of judicial convention of stare decisis nor create uncertainties in the Nigerian legal system nor mete out injustice to the first respondent. However, the reality is that as a result of this judgment, Nigerians have become deeply disillusioned with the judiciary. They are aghast at the many illogical, sometimes contradictory judgments handed down by the Court. The case under review is a typical example. It is submitted that the cause of justice has not been well served by the majority decision of the Court in this case. The only redeeming factor that may save the judiciary from going back to the mediaeval English model of administration of justice and to eliminate the far-reaching consequence of this decision is the expectation that the Court at the earliest opportunity will reverse itself. Otherwise, the lower courts will continue to follow and perpetuate this erroneous decision as the marauding ghost of controversy faced by the lower courts in respect of two conflicting decisions of a higher court has permanently been laid to rest by the Supreme Court in the case of *Osakwe v. Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba* where the Court held that;

For the umpteenth time, where there appear to be conflicting judgment of the Court, the latter or latest will or should apply and must be followed if the circumstances are the same.

This confirms that the latest decision is to serve as the precedent. It is the view of this writer that the judiciary as the sanctuary of justice, the last hope of the common man, the beacon of direction to all and sundry and the third estate of the realm should be above board. It should not only be the last sentinel of democracy but also ensure that the integrity of a judge should be without a shadow of doubt. This is recently reaffirmed by the highest court in the United Kingdom in the following words; “Individually, a judge must also be both honest and incorruptible and independent of the parties and issues before him. Nigeria ought to be basking in the euphoria of achieving a milestone in the current democratic journey which has spanned twenty-four years and still counting. The Court as the highest court of the land should realise that slavish reliance on dry technicalities in this digital age cannot serve the ends of

justice. Justices of the Court should at all times bear in mind the words of admonition of Lord Atkins in *United Australia Ltd. V. Backlays Bank Ltd.* cited with approval in *UTC Ltd v. Panmotei & 4 ors* that says:

“when these ghosts of the past (forms of action) stands in the path of justice, clanking their medieval chains, the proper cause for judges is to pass through them undeterred”.

The Court is too sacred to serve as the cemetery of democracy.